

TECHNOLOGICAL MODES OF SINTERING HARD ALLOY PLATES IN A VACUUM FURNACE WITH ISOSTATIC PRESSING AND THE STUDY OF THEIR PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of experimental studies of the technological process of obtaining hard-alloy plates based on WC-TiC-Co (T5K10). The physical and mechanical properties were studied depending on the temperature, pressure in the vacuum chamber and the sintering environment.*

Keywords: *cemented carbide, vacuum sintering, hardness, bending strength, specific gravity, coercive force.*

Introduction.

Hard alloys based on tungsten carbide in combination with cobalt or nickel to improve ductility and strength are materials with high strength, hardness and wear resistance [1]. They are widely used in various industries, in particular in the production of cutting tools.

The use of hard alloys as cutting tools is due to their ability to retain shape and sharpness even at high temperatures and loads [2]. Hard alloys are used to manufacture various types of cutting tools, such as milling cutters, drills, cutters and turning inserts.

The physical, mechanical, thermal and crystal-chemical properties of the tool material have a strong influence on the performance of the cutting tool, and the optimal choice of a combination of these properties allows one to control the tool wear processes and reduce the wear intensity of the tool contact areas [2].

There are many powder metallurgy methods that are used to sinter hard alloys to improve their physical and mechanical properties and slow down grain growth. These include standard liquid phase sintering (LPS) [3-4], hot isostatic pressing (HIP) [5], and unconventional processes such as microwave sintering [6, 7], spark plasma sintering (SPS) [8–11], high frequency induction-heated sintering (HFIHS) [12, 13], rapid omni compaction (ROC) [14], pulse plasma sintering (PPS) [15], and ultrahigh pressure rapid hot consolidation (UPRC) [16]. All these methods are aimed at preventing grain growth, which begins to increase rapidly at high sintering temperatures.

In this work, hard alloys consisting of tungsten carbide (85%), titanium carbide (5%) and a binding component — cobalt (10%) were investigated. For manufacturing, the method of vacuum sintering with subsequent rapid cooling in an inert gas environment (Ar) was used. The

technological modes of sintering and cooling are described. The physical and mechanical properties of the products are studied.

Materials and methods of research

Experiments to study the sintering method and physical and mechanical properties of WC-TiC-Co (T5K10) hard alloys were conducted at the Uzbek Technological Metals Plant JSC in the hard alloy production shop. Products made of T5K10 hard alloy (WC — 85%, TiC — 5%, Co — 10%) were manufactured using powder metallurgy. The process of preparing the charge includes obtaining tungsten and titanium carbides in carburization furnaces at temperatures of 1400–1500°C, and then grinding them in ball mills. After that, cobalt powder is added to the ground powder mixture. A solution of rubber in gasoline is used as a plasticizer. To give the products the required shape, the charge is pressed on press machines. Samples of rods and products are shown in Figures 1–2.

***Fig. 1. Sample of the staffs:
the color is uniform, metallic shade;
the shape is correct, without deformation;
the dimensions of the pressed raw block are
5.9x6.1x39 mm, the standard of the sintered
block taking into account shrinkage is
5x5x33 mm, the resulting sample is 5x5.1
mmx33mm***

***Fig.2. Samples of products:
the color is uniform, metallic shade;
the shape is correct, without deformation;
The products do not have any external signs
of defects;***

Further sintering was carried out in a PVA TePla COD 633R vacuum furnace with rapid cooling using inert gas Ar.

Vacuum compression sintering furnaces COD PVATePla are designed for universal use for the purpose of removing plasticizer, sintering in a vacuum and subsequent pressing of sintered elements made of hard alloys or technical ceramics under medium vacuum conditions, in an atmosphere of chemically active gases and with increased gas pressure up to 100 bar.

Vacuum compression unit: COD 633 R has the following characteristics:

Working pressure: 60/100 bar;

Useful length: 1000 mm;

Useful volume: 250 l;

Load weight: 800 kg;

Connected power: 400 kW.

Figure 3 shows the general appearance of the COD 633 R installation.

The sintering process included the following stages:

Heating the furnace at a heating rate of $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to a temperature of 300°C for 60 minutes.

Heating the furnace at a heating rate of $6.67^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to a temperature of 800°C for 75 minutes.

Heating the furnace at a heating rate of $8^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to a temperature of 1200°C for 50 minutes.

Heating the furnace at a heating rate of $8.33^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to a temperature of 1450°C for 30 minutes.

Holding at a temperature of 1450°C for 20 minutes in a vacuum environment.

Fig. 3. Installation of PVATePla COD 633 R

Rapid cooling using argon under high pressure of 2 bar with a cooling rate of $11.42^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to a temperature of 80°C within 120 min.

Fig. 4. Technological process of sintering samples from hard alloy grade WC-TiC-Co (T5K10)

Additional studies of the physical and mechanical properties of the samples obtained by vacuum sintering were conducted in laboratory conditions. During the studies, the specific gravity of the samples was determined, their hardness was measured using the Rockwell method, and a bending test was conducted.

Results and discussion

The test results are presented in Table 1. For comparison of the results, data from reference samples corresponding to the requirements of GOST 3882-74 are also provided.

Analyzing the results, we can judge that the selected technological modes are the most optimal. The selected four-stage heating of products to a certain temperature with optimal speeds gave good results. The physical and mechanical properties of WC-TiC-Co (T5K10) carbide plates meet the requirements of the standard. With the selected technological mode, the following was achieved: specific gravity 12.3 - 12.73 g/cm³; hardness (HRC) 90.3-90.5; bending strength 165-167 kgf/mm². These data correspond to the standard GOST values, and mechanical properties such as hardness and bending strength exceed the standard values for such alloys obtained by traditional methods.

Table 1

Physical and mechanical characteristics of the obtained samples

Samples	Specific gravity, g/cm ³		Hardness, HRC		Bending strength, kgf/mm ²		Coercive force, kA/m	
	Value	Standard	Value	Standard	Value	Standard	Value	Standard
Headquarters-1	12.47	Standard according to GOST 3882-74: 12.4-13.1	90.5	Standard according to GOST 3882-74: ≥88.5	167	Standard according to GOST 3882-74: ≥145	9.6	Standard according to GOST 3882-74: 8.0-10.4
Headquarters-2	12.47		90.3		168		9.5	
Headquarters-3	12.44		90.3		165		9.5	
Products-1	12.73		90.5		-		9.5	
Products-2	12.3		90.3		-		9.4	

Conclusions:

By studying the influence of technological processes on the physical and mechanical properties of hard alloys of the WC-TiC-Co (T5K10) brand, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- isostatic pressing in an inert gas atmosphere at a selected sintering temperature allows for uniform compression of samples over the entire surface, which has the most beneficial effect on the properties of the resulting products;
- isostatic pressing units allow rapid cooling using compressed gas from the sintering temperature and using an air blower;
- the obtained samples were of high quality as a result of the highest uniformity of temperature distribution in vacuum and under pressure;
- the obtained results on the physical and mechanical properties of the WC-TiC-Co (T5K10) alloy show that isostatic pressing technology is a promising method for forming hard alloy plates with high mechanical properties.
- the isostatic pressing method can smooth out the shortcomings of the metallurgical process of obtaining powders. It is recommended to conduct a preliminary test for chemical analysis of powders. Strict adherence to the chemical composition and dispersion of the powder material according to the standard allows for additional improvement of the properties of products.

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